

THE EFFECTIVENESS OF THE USE OF MARKETING STRATEGIES IN THE ORGANIZATIONAL AND ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT OF PRIVATE ENTREPRENEURSHIP.

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Abstract

This article presents analytical opinions on the effectiveness of the use of marketing strategies in the organizational and economic development of private entrepreneurship, the Ansoff matrix, the Boston matrix and their essence, the effectiveness of the use of marketing strategies.

Key words

small business and private entrepreneurship, outsourcing services, Ansoff matrix and business development strategies, growth strategy matrix, market matrix, existing market, new market, Boston matrix.

It is important to study foreign experience in the development of small businesses and private entrepreneurship and apply positive experience in Uzbekistan. In developed countries, the activities of small businesses are supported by the state. For example, in Portugal, investments in the development of small enterprises are encouraged by the state. In France, the activities of small businesses are supported by the state through the provision of tax incentives. In Germany, the activity of small enterprises is encouraged by providing subsidies, subsidies for services, preferential loans and financial assistance. In the United States, small businesses are provided with tax incentives, in particular, the state has provided incentives for small businesses in inheritance tax, company registration, financial and technical direction.¹¹¹

In addressing the problem of employment in any market system, small business opportunities deserve special attention. In industrialized countries, it accounts for 50-60% of all employed and 70-80% of new jobs. The table above

¹¹¹ Cambell Mc.Connel, Stanley Brul, Seam Brul. Economics: Principle, Problems and Policies. Izd.: Megran Mill series in Economics, 2014. 327 p

shows the high importance of small business in solving the problem of employment. His analysis shows that more than half of the workers in most developed countries are employed in small businesses. In some countries this figure is much higher. For example, in Japan, 3/4 of the Japanese are employed in small business. The ability of a small business to create a large number of jobs is of paramount importance for our country, where the population and labor force are growing at a rapid pace. Any professional who decides to engage in entrepreneurial activity must be able to control the financial resources of the small enterprise he manages on the basis of accounting, statistics and operational information, as well as be able to solve a number of financial issues related to its analysis.

Table 1

Description of the criteria for identifying small enterprises operating in the industrial sector in foreign countries.

States	Criteria for private enterprise	
	Number of employees, people	Financial indicators
Korea	up to 300	capital, 70 million rubles It should not be more than US dollars.
Japan	up to 300	2844 thousand. U.S. dollars
India	no limits	the value of the asset in terms of fixed assets up to 55 thousand US dollars
Azerbaijan	50	Unlimited
Armenia	200	Unlimited
Belarus	Less than 100	Unlimited
Kazakhstan	Up to 50	the total average annual value of assets must not exceed 60,000 times the minimum wage
Kyrgyzstan	50 people	the maximum turnover is 500 thousand soms
Moldova	20 to 75	Unlimited
Russia	100	annual income up to 400 million rubles
Tajikistan	50 people	Unlimited
Ukraine	200	Unlimited
Uzbekistan	up to 100	Unlimited

Based on the analysis of the criteria for identifying small enterprises operating in the industrial sector in foreign countries, it is advisable to use indicators that

reflect the financial results of their activities, as well as the number of employees as a criterion for distinguishing small enterprises in the industry. It is appropriate to take into account the book value and profitability of the company's assets.

Any specialist who decides to engage in entrepreneurial activity must be able to control the financial resources of the small enterprise he manages on the basis of accounting, statistics and operational information, and also be able to solve a number of financial issues related to its analysis. The head of each small business entity may not have enough knowledge to independently conduct accounting, since they are representatives of different areas. As a result, a small error in accounting leads to inaccuracies in the calculations and payments of taxes, or an error in the original document is reflected in the financial statements. The outsourcing service is a relatively new concept for the practice of our republic, with the help of its implementation, small businesses can avoid excessive time spent on searching, collecting and processing information, duplicating documents and providing fuzzy information for the development of their activities, will be free.

In the development of small businesses, it is considered appropriate to use certain types of marketing strategies.

Marketing strategy refers to the methods you apply to promote your products and services to your target audience. This may include website content, television and radio advertisements, and content posted on social media platforms. Developing an effective marketing strategy for your business is the key to growth, expansion and long-term success. The problem, however, is that developing the right marketing strategy can lead to many failures, and for small businesses, the cost of misunderstanding your market can be catastrophic.¹¹²

One such strategy is the Ansoff matrix and business development strategies.

Igor Ansoff's Growth Strategy Matrix is a model that describes possible strategies for private businesses to increase their market share. The matrix is also called the product-market matrix. The Ansoff matrix is widely used in practice in the process of managing strategic enterprises.¹¹³

In his commodity market model, Igor Ansoff suggested implementing four possible growth strategies for business development:

1. Market entry strategy: Growth means increasing the market share of the current product.
2. Market development strategy: refers to the growth of private enterprises through the development of demand in new markets.

¹¹² <https://smallbusiness.chron.com/advantages-disadvantages-marketing-strategy-53961.html>

¹¹³ <http://powerbranding.ru/biznes-analiz/matrica-ansoffa/>

3. Product development strategy: means that the source of growth of private enterprises is the growth in demand for new products.

4. Diversification strategy means renewing the product range and entering new markets at the same time.

It would be appropriate if private businesses used the Ansoff matrix. Because determining the market of existing consumers in the market, attracting new consumers, evaluating the market of productive and unproductive consumers is one of the important tasks facing private business entities. Because in the current process of globalization, every enterprise needs to maximize profits in the domestic and foreign markets, maintain its position in the market and operate for a long period of time.

When analyzing the market conditions of private enterprises, one of the marketing strategies that we consider especially important in the market of global multinational companies is the Boston matrix.

The BCG matrix is a tool for strategic analysis, planning and marketing. Founded by Bruce D. Henderson, a Boston-based consulting group founded to analyze the relevance of the company's products, exit from the ninth position in the market regarding the growth in demand for these products and the market share occupied by the company chosen for analysis.

The axes of the matrix reflect demand growth (vertical axis) and market share (horizontal axis). Combining the ratings of these two customers makes it possible to classify the goods, highlighting four possible roles for goods for the production and sale of the company's ego.¹¹⁴

Classifications of types of strategic business units:

- Stars - High sales growth and high market share. Market share must be maintained and increased. "Stars" bring a very large income. But, despite the attractiveness of this product, its net cash flow is quite low, as it requires significant investment to ensure a high growth rate.

- Cash Cows (Money Bags, Cream) - High market share but low sales growth. "Cash cows" must be protected and controlled as much as possible. Their attractiveness is explained by the fact that they do not require additional investments and at the same time provide a good cash income. Proceeds from sales can be directed to the development of "Difficult Children" and to support the "Stars".

¹¹⁴ https://ru.wikipedia.org/wiki/Матрица_БКГ

• Difficult Children (Wild Cats, Dark Horses, Question Marks, Trouble, Calves) Low market share but strong growth. Difficult children need to be studied. In the future, they can become both stars and dogs. If there is a possibility of transfer to the stars, then you need to invest, otherwise, get rid of it.

• "Dogs" ("Losers", "Lame Ducks", "Dead Weight") - growth rate is low, market share is low, the product, as a rule, has a low level of profitability and requires a lot of attention from the manager. Get rid of dogs.

Based on the above information, we have come to the following conclusion.

The following efficiency can be achieved by using marketing strategies in private business.

1. As a result of the implementation of marketing strategies, you will determine the audience of target consumers. As a result, before developing a marketing strategy, you must do market research, and this research will provide you with a wealth of information that you can use over and over again to improve your product and track events and changes in your behavior.

2. Using marketing strategies will help you brand your business. As a result, your marketing strategy will not only help you reach potential customers and turn them into buyers, it will also help you express your business culture, values, and goals. The process of communicating this vision to your audience is the essence of branding.

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